

Soil alterations due to flooding: An examination of morphological and physical properties of soils in imo and Anambra states, Nigeria

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Abstract

The morphological and physical properties of soils largely determine their behaviour, productivity and resilience to flooding in low-lying ecosystems. Soil samples were collected from six high-risk flood locations in Imo and Anambra States at 0–15 cm, 15–30 cm and 30–45 cm depths, with two control samples from elevated non-flooded towns. Results showed significant differences in colour, structure, drainage and texture reflecting local hydrological regimes. Floodplain sites such as Akili-Ozizor, Atani and Odekpe exhibited olive to grey gleyic hues, poor drainage and medium subangular blocky structures, features typical of prolonged saturation and iron reduction. In contrast, the upland control at Ihiala displayed reddish, well-drained profiles with friable consistencies. Hydromorphic patterns were also observed at Abacheke, Ekeugba and Mmahu, where dark greyish colours and fine roots indicated fluctuating water tables and limited pedogenic development. Particle-size analysis revealed predominantly sandy clay to clay loam textures, with clay enrichment up to 410 g kg⁻¹ at Abacheke and Amafor linked to sedimentation during floods. Sand-to-clay ratios, bulk density (1.27–1.44 Mg m⁻³), total porosity (45–52%) and gravimetric moisture (10–25%) varied widely, reflecting microtopographic influences on drainage, aeration and compaction. High porosity and moisture in Amafor and Ihiala favoured water retention, whereas higher bulk density and lower porosity in Akili-Ozizor suggested greater susceptibility to waterlogging and restricted root growth. These findings underscore the strong influence of flooding, sediment dynamics and soil physical properties on land use and floodplain agriculture, where texture, bulk density and porosity shape crop suitability, nutrient cycling and microbial activity under recurrent inundation.

Keywords: Flooding; Morphology; Physical Properties; Hydromorphism

1. Introduction

Flooding is defined as the temporary overflow or accumulation of water onto land that is normally dry. [1]. Over the years, South-east Nigeria has experienced a series of recurring and increasingly severe flood events due to both climatic and anthropogenic factors [2]. Climate variability and change, characterized by more intense short-duration rainfall events and alterations in seasonal patterns, have been widely recognized as contributing to the heightened flood risk across Nigeria [2]. When soils are inundated, oxygen is displaced from pore spaces, pushing conditions from aerobic toward anaerobic. This shift reduces the effectiveness of soil microorganisms that depend on oxygen, thereby favoring anaerobic microbes that thrive without oxygen. Nutrient cycles, particularly for nitrogen, carbon, phosphorus, and iron, are disrupted: for instance, denitrification may increase, making nitrogen gases escape into the atmosphere. Iron and manganese oxides can dissolve under reduced conditions, altering soil fertility [3]. Flooding alters soils biochemistry through multiple, interacting mechanisms: Flooded soils become oxygen deprived, quickly shifting soil redox potential

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[3]. Floodwaters promote soluble nutrient transport (particularly nitrate and dissolved organic carbon) and, under anaerobic conditions, increase gaseous N losses (denitrification) together worsening soil fertility and altering plant nutrient availability [4]. Aerobic microbes are suppressed while anaerobic taxa proliferate; processes like denitrification, sulfate reduction and methanogenesis accelerate under low oxygen (O₂). These changes alter nutrient availability and greenhouse-gas fluxes [4][5]. Flooding commonly reduces activities of some extracellular enzymes and shifts microbial community composition: obligate aerobes decline and anaerobic or facultative organisms increase, with consequences for decomposition rates and nutrient cycling [5]. Rapid infiltration and saturated conditions can lead to compaction when machinery or trampling occurs after flooding; alternation between flooding and drying also affects aggregate stability and porosity [6] [7]. Floodwaters mobilise sediments and contaminants (heavy metals, hydrocarbons, pathogens) from upstream or contaminated urban/industrial areas, depositing them on floodplains and farmland. This can produce short- and long-term contamination risks for agriculture and human health. [7] [8]. Therefore, the aim of this research is to examine the morphological and physical properties of soils in Imo and Anambra states, Nigeria.

2. Materials and Method

2.1. Study Area

The study areas, Ohaji- egbema, Ihiala and Ogbaru in (Southeastern) Nigeria, is made up of five Igbo speaking States which includes; Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo. These States constitute one of the six geo-political zones in Nigeria. It is located between latitudes 4 ° 20' to 7 ° 10' north of the equator and longitudes 6 ° 35' to 8 ° 25' east of the Greenwich Meridian with a land size of about 28,983km². The region is bounded to the north by Benue and Kogi States, to the south by Rivers State, to the east by Cross River State and to the west by Delta State.

Source: Garwin Ltd USA (2024)

Figure 1 Maps of Nigeria showing the Geographical and Sampling Points in Ohaji-Egbema L.G.A. of Imo State and Ihiala and Ogbaru L.G.A. of Anambra State

2.1.1. Field Study

Soil samples were collected from six distinct high risk flood locations in southeast, Nigeria, using soil auger. At each location, soil samples were gridded and collected with depths; 0–15cm, 15– 30cm and 30– 45cm, representing top soil, sub soil and bottom soils respectively. One control sample was also collected from high elevation town within the region, not affected by flood. The sampling site/points were geo-referenced via GPS coordinates for accurate map generation. A total of eight (8) soil samples were collected in the month of October, 2024, a transition period from rainy session to dry session, the reason for the period is simply to regulate leachate migration in the soil. The soil samples were air-dried in a clean well – ventilated laboratory [9] homogenized by grinding, passed through a 2mm (10mesh) stainless sieve and stored in labeled plastic cans ready for analysis. However, the use of soil auger for sampling and subsequent air-drying and sieving were adopted in other to preserve the quality of the sample. The soil auger allowed for the collection of consistent soil cores, promoting uniform sample depth and minimizing contamination from other layers. In other to reduce moisture content and as well preserve the chemical composition of soil, air drying method were used while 2mm sieve mesh helps to remove debris and larger stones thereby promoting homogeneity of samples,

2.1.2. Location

The study area, Ohaji-Egbema in Imo state (Southeastern) Nigeria, is made up of five Igbo speaking States which includes; Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo. These States constitute one of the six geo-political zones in Nigeria. It is located between latitudes 4 ° 20' to 7 ° 10' north of the equator and longitudes 6 ° 35' to 8 ° 25' east of the Greenwich Meridian with a land size of about 28,983km². The region is bounded to the north by Benue and Kogi States, to the south by Rivers State, to the east by Cross River State and to the west by Delta State. Ohaji-Egbema in Imo States was selected for this study since it is among the Local Government Areas severely affected in Imo States since 2012 flood event. Imo State lies between latitude 5 ° 10'N to 5 ° 25'N and longitude 6 ° 35'E to 7 ° 23'E of the Greenwich meridian with a total land area of about 5,183sqkm.

2.1.3. Climate

Southeastern Nigeria lies within tropical wet-and-dry climate or Aw climate based on Koppen's climate classification. It usually experiences an average of eight months of rainfall and four months of dry season. The two major seasons experienced in this region are; the rainy season (March to October) and the dry season (November to February). Heaviest rainfall usually occurs in July and September while December records the driest month while the month of March records the hottest weather. Mean annual rainfall ranges from 1800mm to 2000mm. It experiences high temperatures all year round with an average value of 27°C while the average relative humidity ranges between 60-70% and 80-90% in January and July respectively. Floods in south eastern Nigeria, are greatly influence by the rainfall pattern, and are usually experienced between July and October which is also the harvest season for most crops.

2.2. Methods

Soil profile morphological characteristics studied included soil color, texture, consistence, structure. Soil color was determined by Munsell soil color charts [10]. Texture was determined by Bouyoucos hydrometer method [11]. Bulk density was determined by the core method of Grossman and Reinsch [12]. Total porosity was calculated from particle and bulk densities using the relationship by Brady and Weil [13]; $TP = \left(1 - \frac{Bd}{Pd}\right) \times 100$ Where: TP = Total porosity (%), Bd = Bulk density (Mg/m³), Pd = Particle density (Mg/m³). Moisture content was determined as outlined by Obi [14].

2.3. Statistical Analysis

Data generated were analyzed using SPSS statistical software package (Version 23.0). All data were presented as the mean and standard deviation values of three replicate, where multiple comparison were done using post hoc to determine which pair of means was significantly different from each other.

3. Results

Table 1 outlines the morphological properties of soil samples collected in Akili-Ozizor, Atani, Odekpe, Ihiala in Anambra and Abacheke, Mmahu, Ekeugba, Amafor in Imo States.

Soil samples from flooded regions in Akili-ozizor, Atani and Odekpe (Anambra State) and Abacheke, Ekeugba (Imo State) exhibited grey colours such as olive (e.g. 5Y5/3), dark grayish brown (2.5Y4/2) and blue-gray hues (5Y3/2) particularly at deeper horizons while the control regions had dark red (10R3/6) and (2.5YR3/6) at deeper horizons. Roots are consistently classified as fine root while Ekeugba were very fill. The soil structures includes: massive subangular blocky (MSBK) and fine crumb (FCR), with more aggregate structures at depth. Poorly drainage (PD) dominated in floodplains

of Atani, Akili-Ozizor, Odekpe and Abacheke. Both control regions exhibited well drainage. Top (shallow) soil layers are usually friable while bottom (deep) layers are firm indicating compaction.

Table 2 presents the physical properties of soil samples in Akili-Ozizor, Atani, Odekpe, Ihiala in Anambra State and Abacheke, Mmahu, Ekeugba, Amafor in Imo state

Across locations, there is no statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in sand, silt, clay and SCR. Abacheke and Amafor exhibited highest values for clay; 410.000g/kg. Both control locations exhibited lower bulk density thus significant at ($p < 0.05$) compared with the flood- affected locations. Total porosity and Gravimetric moisture showed a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) when compared with other flood -affected locations.

Table 1 Result of Soil Morphological Properties in Akili-Ozizor, Atani, Odekpe, Ihiala in Anambra State

Locations	Depth (cm)	Colour	Roots	Structure	Drainage	Consistency
Akili-Ozizor	0-15	O(5Y5/3)	Fine root	1FCR	PD	Friable
Akili-Ozizor	15-30	PO(5Y6/4)	Fine root	2MSBK	PD	Friable
Akili-Ozizor	30-45	OY(5Y6/8)	Fine root	2MSBK	PD	Firm
Atani	0-15	OG(5Y4/2)	Fine root	2FRGR	PD	Friable
Atani	15-30	O(5Y4/3)	Fine root	2MSBK	PD	Firm
Atani	30-45	O(5Y5/6)	Fine root	3MSBK	PD	Firm
Odekpe	0-15	LYB (2.5Y4/2)	Fine root	1FCR	PD	Friable
Odekpe	15-30	DGB (2.5Y4/2)	Fine root	2MSBK	PD	Firm
Odekpe	30-45	GB (2.5Y5/2)	Fine root	2MSBK	PD	Firm
Ihiala (control)	0-15	DRB(2.5YR3/3)	Fine root	1FGR	WD	Friable
Ihiala (control)	15-30	R(2.5YR5/6)	Fine root	2MGR	WD	Friable
Ihiala (control)	30-45	DR (10R3/6)	Fine root	3MSBK	WD	Firm

PD: poor drainage, WD: well drainage

Table 2 Result of Soil Morphological Properties in Abacheke, Mmahu, Ekeugba, Amafor in Imo State

Locations	Depth (cm)	Colour	Roots	Structure	Drainage	Consistency
Abacheke	0-15	G(2.5Y6 2)	Fine root	IFGR	ID	Firm
Abacheke	15-30	DGB (2.5Y4/2)	Fine root	2MSBK	ID	Firm
Abacheke	30-45	GB(2.5Y3 2)	Fine root	3MSBK	ID	Firm
Mmahu	0-15	DOG(5Y3/2)	Very fill	2FBK	WD	Friable
Mmahu	15-30	VDG(5Y3/1)	Fine root	1FGR	WD	Friable
Mmahu	30-45	B (5Y2.5/2)	Fine root	2MFSK	WD	Firm
Ekeugba	0-15	B (2.5Y2.5/1)	Very fill	1FCR	ID	Friable
Ekeugba	15-30	DGB (2.5Y4/2)	Very fill	2MSBK	ID	Friable
Ekeugba	30-45	LOB (2.5Y5/4)	Very fill	3MSBK	ID	Firm
Amafor(control)	0-15	RB(5YR4/3)	Fine root	IFGR	WD	Friable
Amafor (control)	15-30	YR(5YR4/6)	Fine root	2MSBK	WD	Friable
Amafor (control)	30-45	DR(2.5YR3/6)	Fine root	2MSBK	WD	Friable

PD: poor drainage, WD: well drainage

Table 3 Result of Soil Physical Properties in Anambra and in Imo States

Locations	Sand (g/kg)	Silt(g/kg)	Clay (g/kg)	SCR	BD (mg/m ³)	TP	GM
			Anambra State				
Akili-Ozizor	433.33±90.73 ^a	256.67±20.82 ^c	336.6667±110.51 ^a	0.8033±0.22 ^b	1.4433±0.07 ^b	45.5300±2.51 ^a	11.3333±0.64 ^a
Atani	433.33±75.06 ^a	223.33±32.15 ^b	343.3333±55.08 ^a	0.6567±0.11 ^b	1.4067±0.08 ^{ab}	46.9133±2.89 ^{ab}	10.5667±0.31 ^a
Odekpe	436.67±76.38 ^a	206.67±15.28 ^b	356.6667±65.06 ^a	0.5867±0.78 ^b	1.4200±0.09 ^b	46.4100±3.40 ^a	10.5333±0.42 ^a
Ihiala	423.33±130.51 ^a	216.67±23.09 ^b	360.0000±52.92 ^a	0.6000±0.66 ^b	1.2733±0.08 ^a	51.9433±2.83 ^b	24.6667±9.55 ^b
			Imo State				
Abacheke	493.33±105.36 ^a	96.67±15.28 ^a	410.0000±145.26 ^a	0.2633±0.14 ^a	1.4267±0.07 ^b	46.1600±2.57 ^a	17.6667±6.81 ^{ab}
Mmahu	500.00±105.36 ^a	126.67±11.55 ^a	373.3333±96.09 ^a	0.3467±0.08 ^a	1.3900±0.07 ^{ab}	47.5433±2.72 ^{ab}	15.4333±4.46 ^{ab}
Ekeugba	486.67±105.99 ^a	130.00±5.00 ^a	383.3333±101.04 ^a	0.3500±0.89 ^a	1.4233±0.07 ^b	46.2833±2.45 ^a	15.7333±5.06 ^{ab}
Amafor	460.00±111.36 ^a	130.00±10.00 ^a	410.0000±121.24 ^a	0.3433±0.14 ^a	1.2700±0.09 ^a	52.0700±3.22 ^b	24.3333±8.75 ^b

Values represent mean±SD of triplicate values while columns with different superscript alphabets are statistically significant (p<0.05).

4. Discussion

The morphological properties of soils are crucial parameters for understanding the behavior, functionality and potential uses of soils. Results across Akili-Ozizor, Atani, Odekpe, Ihiala (Anambra State) and Abacheke, Mmahu, Ekeugba, Amafor (Imo State) revealed significant differences in colour, structure, drainage, and consistency with depth. Soils at Akili-Ozizor and Atani exhibit olive and yellow hues (5Y), fine roots, and predominantly medium subangular blocky structures with poor drainage (PD) and friable to firm consistencies. This reflects a floodplain environment where prolonged water saturation promotes reducing conditions that impart greyish or olive gleyed colours due to iron reduction and mobilization [15].

Soils in Odekpe also display gleyed colours (2.5Y) with poor drainage and medium subangular blocky structures, indicating alluvial deposition and seasonal flooding. By contrast, the control site at Ihiala shows reddish hues (2.5YR), well-drained (WD) profiles, and friable consistencies typical of upland, better-aerated soils. The differences suggest that flooding and drainage status exert strong control on morphological properties.

Profiles from Ohaji-egbema show similar trends: Abacheke and Ekeugba have greyish or dark greyish colours (2.5Y), indicative of hydromorphic conditions and impeded drainage (ID), while Mmahu shows dark olive to black colours at depth with well-drained conditions, suggesting mixed fluvial and upland influences. This agrees with earlier findings that floodplain soils in southeastern Nigeria tend to be gleyic, poorly drained, and with weak to moderate subangular blocky structures due to seasonal inundation [16] [17].

The presence of fine roots throughout the horizons, despite poor drainage, indicates vegetation adapted to fluctuating water tables. Structural variations from fine crumb (FCR) at the surface to medium or coarse subangular blocky (MSBK) at depth are typical of hydromorphic soils where periodic saturation limits pedogenic development.). Similar hydromorphic colour patterns have been reported in southeastern Nigeria's floodplains [18] [19].

The particle size distribution results reveal that the soils across the studied floodplains are predominantly sandy clay to clay loam in texture, with sand fractions ranging from 423.33 to 500 g/kg, silt fractions from 96.67 to 256.67 g/kg, and clay fractions from 336.67 to 410 g/kg. The relatively high clay content, particularly in Abacheke (410 g/kg) and Amafor (410 g/kg), reflects the depositional nature of floodplains, where fine particles tend to accumulate due to sedimentation processes during inundation. Such clay-rich soils often have higher water and nutrient retention capacities, but when combined with frequent flooding, they may develop poor aeration and slow drainage, predisposing them to anaerobic conditions [20].

The sand-to-clay ratio (SCR) ranged from 0.2633 in Abacheke to 0.8033 in Akili-Ozizor. Lower SCR values, as observed in Abacheke, Amafor, and Ekeugba, suggest dominance of fine-textured soils that are structurally compact and less permeable [21]. Conversely, relatively higher SCR values in Akili-Ozizor and Atani indicate a more balanced textural composition, which may enhance drainage and aeration. These differences are consistent with microtopographic variations within floodplains, which influence sediment sorting and deposition [22].

Bulk density (BD) values ranged from 1.27 mg/m³ in Ihiala and Amafor to 1.44 mg/m³ in Akili-Ozizor. The comparatively lower BD in Ihiala and Amafor suggests higher organic matter incorporation, better aggregation, and lower compaction, characteristics often linked with higher biological activity and organic inputs in low-lying floodplains [23]. By contrast, higher BD values in Akili-Ozizor may indicate soil compaction due to repeated flooding and sediment deposition. Flooding can increase bulk density through sediment layering and loss of soil organic matter [24]. The observed BD values are within the moderate range for agricultural soils, but values above 1.4 mg/m³ (as in Akili-Ozizor and Abacheke) could begin to restrict root penetration and water movement [25].

Total porosity (TP) varied significantly among sites, with Amafor and Ihiala recording the highest values (52.07% and 51.94%, respectively), while Akili-Ozizor had the lowest (45.53%). High porosity in Amafor and Ihiala supports better aeration and moisture infiltration, favoring root growth and microbial activity [26]. Conversely, lower porosity in Akili-Ozizor aligns with its higher BD, implying reduced pore space and increased susceptibility to waterlogging during floods.

Gravimetric moisture (GM) values showed distinct variability, ranging from 10.53% in Odekpe to 24.67% in Ihiala. The higher GM observed in Ihiala and Amafor corresponds with their elevated porosity and finer texture, which enhances water retention [27]. In contrast, the relatively lower GM in Atani and Odekpe may reflect coarser fractions and better drainage. Floodplain soils often show strong spatial variation in water retention, influenced by textural heterogeneity and hydrological gradients [28].

5. Conclusion

Morphological analyses showed clear indications of hydromorphism in flooded soils, including low chroma values, hard consistencies in subsurface strata that confirmed prolonged saturation, and grey mottling.

The physical properties indicated that the floodplain soils of Anambra and Imo States are characterized by heterogeneity in texture and structural properties. Fine-textured sites such as Abacheke and Amafor are predisposed to higher moisture retention and reduced aeration, while coarser or balanced sites like Atani and Akili-Ozizor may have better drainage but are prone to compaction.

Compliance with ethical standards

Soil sampling was conducted in accordance with ASTM D1452-09. Samples were collected with minimal disturbance to the environment, and proper handling and storage procedures were followed to prevent contamination. Informed consent was obtained from communities/participants, and their confidentiality maintained throughout the study

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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